

MULTI-SCALE ANALYSIS OF EFFECTS OF CONSTITUENT PROPERTIES ON OPEN-HOLE TENSION PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Abstract

The effect of constituent properties on open-hole tension performance of CFRP was studied by means of a combination of experiments and numerical simulations. A new stress-based multi-scale failure model was proposed, in which failure criteria of constituents were carefully determined based on experimental results. Open-hole tension performance of three material systems (T300/5228, T300/5428, T700/5428) were examined. Good agreements were found between the experimental results and the numerical simulations. It was found that fiber strength was a key factor influencing ultimate strength of the laminates, while matrix property degradation alleviated the stress concentration. The relative strength of fiber and matrix determined the OHT strength and failure mode, as well as types and extent of internal damage in the notched composites prior to failure.

Keywords: *Composite laminate, multi-scale, constituent properties, open-hole tension*

1 Introduction

Due to high ratio of strength/stiffness to weight and good corrosion resistance etc., fiber-reinforced composite materials are being widely used in modern aero-plane structures, which have been demonstrated that primary aircraft structures made from carbon fiber composites can achieve weight savings of 20% to 30% over similarly designed metal structures. Airbus uses 25% composites in A380 structures and Boeing uses up to 50% in B787, and the percentage of composite materials used in commercial jet aero-planes becomes a symbol of technology advantage and market competitiveness^[1]. As its great importance to structure safety, failure behavior and strength prediction of composite materials have been studied extensively in the literature. For several decades development, countless efforts have been made in this area, and substantial achievements have been obtained^[2]. Some well-known failure criteria like Tsai-Wu tensor criterion^[3], Hashin criterion^[4] etc. can effectively predict failure strength of composites and have been widely used in engineering practices. The World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE) sponsored by Hinton^[5] provides a good opportunity for comparison of all the participant failure theories against experimental results, and comprehensive assessment of 19 leading failure theories was presented, including their validities and shortfalls. All theories were ranked according to their abilities to predict a wide range of experimental results.

To fully investigate the performance of composite materials, some failure theories based on

micromechanics were developed these years. Goose^[6] proposed Strain invariant failure theory (SIFT) in 2001, which identifies fiber and matrix failure by two strain invariants in micro-level and attributes matrix failure to dilatation as well as distortion failure. The Multi-continuum Theory (MCT) by Mayes et al.^[7], in which constitutive equations of fiber and matrix are formulated respectively by stress at a point, identifying their failures by quadratic stress failure criterion. Considering the failure of fiber, matrix and interface, the Micro-Mechanics of failure (MMF) criterion proposed by Sung Kyu Ha et al^[8] formulates damage determination and evolution methods recently. Brett A. Bednarczyk et al.^[9] uses a micromechanics model called the Generalized Method of Cells to evaluate failure criteria at the micro-level, and corresponding analysis platform FEAMAC is presented. Up to now, multi-scale failure criteria have been used in fracture and durability analyses of composite structures to some extent^[10-12], and this theory takes its advantage in the discussion of temperature and fiber volume fraction's effects on material's mechanical behavior^[13, 14]. However, the multi-scale failure criteria still require considerable improvements. Problems such as the transition between micro- and macro-levels, identification and evolution of failure modes in micro-level are still suspended.

The main purpose of this paper is to investigate effects of constituent properties on open-hole tension performance of composite laminates via a revised multi-scale failure model, which attempts to improve practical application of multi-scale method and solve some potential problems in the procedures

of application. Based on experimental observations, failure behaviors of fiber and matrix at meso level were redefined, square and hexagon representative volume elements (RVE) were introduced to characterize stress distribution between constituents, and the updating methods of stress amplification factors and ply property were established. Open-hole tension test was chosen as a benchmark to validate the potential of this method because it has complexity of both geometry and stress state, which can fully embody the difference of composite constituents and has been adopted as the industry standard for determining the damage tolerance performance of FRP laminates^[15]. In this paper, open-hole tension specimens of three material systems (T300/5228, T300/5428, and T700/5428) were examined, after validated experimentally, the numerical model was used to assess the effect of constituent properties on the OHT behavior of CFRP laminates.

2 Proposal of multi-scale failure model for composites

2.1 Transformation from macro stresses to micro stresses

As is the average value of fiber and matrix within the section in macro-level, stress value obtained by mechanical experiments in laminates can't describe the actual stress distribution in micro-level. However, under the arrangement assumption of fiber and matrix, stress applied on single layer can be equivalent to the stress applied on RVE, as can be seen in Fig. 1.

Therefore, we can obtain micro stresses in fiber and matrix from its counterpart in macro-level by FE analyses on RVEs, which can be written using stress amplification factors:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{M}_{\sigma} \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} + \mathbf{A}_{\sigma} \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ 、 $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ (6×1) are micro and macro stress vectors respectively, \mathbf{M}_{σ} (6×6) is the matrix of mechanical stress amplification factors caused by different mechanical behaviors of fiber and matrix, and \mathbf{A}_{σ} (6×1) is the matrix of thermal stress amplification factors caused by their different thermal coefficients. The derivations of \mathbf{M}_{σ} and \mathbf{A}_{σ} are introduced in detail in reference^[11].

Fig. 2 is the representative distributions of fiber and matrix considered in this paper, so square and

hexagon RVEs were used to obtain stress amplification factors and to determine damage initiation as well as evolution. The FEM models of square and hexagon RVEs as well as their coordinate directions are shown in Fig. 3, where 1 describes fiber direction and 2, 3 are the normal directions of fiber. Due to the symmetry of RVEs and stress distribution, all reference points in the above mentioned two unit cell models are in the upper side of the model. In the RVE of square, 6 out of 16 are in the fiber and the other 10 are in the matrix, while in the RVE of hexagon, 8 out of 21 are in the fiber and the other 13 are in the matrix. Mechanical and thermo-mechanical amplification factors in eq. (1) of each reference point can be obtained, which is of great importance in the judging of failure of fiber and matrix. In general circumstances, some differences between the stress amplification factors of square and hexagon RVE models exist and should be taken into consideration when carrying out failure judgment.

2.2 Characterization of meso failure modes

Unlike traditional metal materials, composites are made up of two constituents with a large mismatch in mechanical and thermal properties, in which fracture can be distinguished in fiber or matrix depending on specific loading conditions. Here we use a revised multi-scale failure criterion which can refer in^[16]. Fiber failure was divided into fiber tensile failure and compressive failure, and matrix failure was divided into dilatational failure and distortional failure.

The maximum longitudinal stress was used to define fiber failure:

(1) Fiber tensile failure:

$$\sigma_{f1} > X_{ft} , \sigma_{f1} > 0 \quad (2)$$

(2) Fiber compressive failure:

$$\sigma_{f1} < -X_{fc} , \sigma_{f1} \leq 0 \quad (3)$$

In the aspect of matrix, L. E. Asp et al.^[17] found that while matrix is constrained between fibers, yielding is suppressed while brittle failure occurs, which is presumably caused by crack growth from cavitation. Failure envelope for polymers in composites is shown in Fig. 4. So two failure mechanisms of matrix should be defined, one is dilatational failure and the other is distortional failure.

Two stress invariants I_1 and σ_{VM} were introduced to characterize the stress state of matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \sigma_{xx} + \sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{zz} \\ I_2 &= \sigma_{xx}\sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{yy}\sigma_{zz} + \sigma_{xx}\sigma_{zz} - (\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{xz}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2) \\ \sigma_{VM} &= \sqrt{I_1^2 - 3I_2} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where I_1 is the volumetric stress invariant, and σ_{VM} is the deviatoric stress invariant. Based on the experiment results, matrix failure can thus be defined as:

(3) Matrix dilatational failure:

$$I_1 + \mu\sigma_{VM}^2 > I_{1-crit} \quad (5)$$

(4) matrix distortional failure:

$$\sigma_{VM} > \sigma_{VM-crit} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 5 is the failure envelope of matrix.

Critical values of multi-scale failure criterion i.e. X_{ft} , X_{fc} , I_{1-crit} , $\sigma_{VM-crit}$ and μ can be obtained from corresponding experiments in Table 1. Macro strengths were introduced into the RVEs, and the maximum values in reference points of fiber and matrix were identified as the critical values.

2.3 Damage determination and evolution

The procedures of damage determination and evolution by multi-scale criterion are shown in Fig. 6. Firstly, apply displacement increment on the FEM model, and get macro stresses $\bar{\sigma}$ of each element. Secondly, calculate micro stresses acquired from macro stresses by equation (1) in reference points of square and hexagon RVE models. Then check whether damage occurs by failure criteria of fiber or matrix in equation (2), (3), (5), (6). If damage doesn't happen, the calculation will go to the next iteration directly. Else if any sort of damage happens, material property should be degraded based on the category of damage and a new iteration can be executed. Once a sharp decrease of load occurs, the FEM analysis will be terminated, and the maximum value of load and displacement will be outputted.

In the process of damage determination, reference points in matrix and fiber must be applied to designated failure criteria respectively. Moreover, the degradation of macro mechanical properties will be executed in different ways due to different failure modes. When fiber failure happens, the longitudinal moduli of fiber in RVE models will be degraded,

and macro property under failure conditions can be derived through the calculation of RVE model. Corresponding procedure will be carried out when failures happen to matrix. After failure occurred, stress amplification factors should also be regenerated. Details of failure determination and material property degradation are listed in Table 2.

3 Experiments

3.1 Materials and specimen preparation

In the respect of experiments, three CFRP material systems were studied, which are T300/5228, T300/5428 and T700/5428. The specimen preparation and test procedure were based on ASTM Standard D5766. Fig. 7 shows the geometry of the OHT specimens. All the three kinds of OHT specimens tested has the size of 250mm×36mm and d/W ratio of 1/6, where d is the hole diameter and W is the laminate width.

Quasi-isotropic type stacking sequence of [45/0/-45/90]_{3s} was chosen since it's very common in aircraft structures, and the thickness of individual ply is 0.125mm. Panels prepared from prepregs were cured in an autoclave according to ASTM D5687. Test specimens were cut from the panels using a dedicated composite cutting machine with a diamond-coated cutting blade. In order to examine the initial defect (like delamination at the edge of the drilled hole) of the specimens, non-destructive testing (NDT) of ultrasonic scan was carried out before experiment.

3.2 Experiment results and damage characterization

Five specimens for each material system were tested to failure to determine the average OHT strength as well as the load- displacement curve. Fig. 8, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 show the load-displacement curves and fracture morphologies of open-hole tension specimens for each of the material systems. The ultimate strength of T300/5228 (325MPa) was not far from T300/5428 (375MPa), and the difference was mainly caused by the type of matrix. T700/5428 has a much higher strength (517MPa) than the T300/5228 and T300/5428 laminates, which is attributed to the much higher strength of T700 fiber. From fracture morphologies we can see that open-hole tension specimens of T300/5228 failed in a brittle manner, with a fairly clean fracture perpendicular to the loading direction, while more extensive damage occurs prior to failure in specimens of T300/5428 with ply-cracking across

the entire width of the specimen, which was more evident in plies close to the surface. Moreover, T700/5428 shows considerable fiber pull-out and ply cracking at final failure accompanied with delamination between some of the exterior plies. It is clear from the curves that all kinds of open-hole tension specimens have a fairly linear load-displacement relation until the curve drops abruptly, except for a small descent in T700/5428 in the vicinity of ultimate strength. The linear nature of the load-displacement curves of all three types of open-hole tension specimens suggests that the failure mechanisms of these tests are brittle or pull-out, where drop of the curves is controlled by 0° fiber breakage.

4 Numerical simulation and discussion

The experimental results above have demonstrated that open-hole tension failure of carbon fiber reinforced composites is rather complex due to the interaction of various failure modes and micromechanical properties. In order to demonstrate the feasibility of multi-scale failure model and to in-depth understand the role of constituent properties played in open-hole tension response, all the test cases were simulated using finite element software ABAQUS. Numerical results were compared with experimental results, and discussions were made.

4.1 Modeling of open-hole tension laminates

The modeling strategy to simulate the quasi-isotropic laminates $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$ with open hole under tension is depicted in Fig. 11. In consideration of computational efficiency, only the center portion around the hole of the specimen was simulated, where stress concentration occurs and critical damage takes place. Because of the in-plane symmetry of the stacking sequence, one half of the specimen was modeled, applying symmetric boundary conditions in the middle plane. The dimension size was $54 \times 36 \times 1.5\text{mm}$ (each ply thickness was 0.125mm), and 12 plies with material orientations of three repeated stacking sequence $45/0/-45/90$ were modeled, with 11 interfaces between each two plies. The radius of the centered hole was $r = 6.0\text{mm}$. One side of the laminate was fixed and uniform displacement was applied to the other side. The areas highlighted in Fig. 11 were contact without damage judgment to prevent premature failure due to boundary effects. Multi-scale failure criterion was applied to plies of the remnant part to simulate progressive failure of the laminate.

As it's a fully three-dimensional failure theory, inter-ply damage were also considered in the model, although it's not a critical issue in the experiments of this paper. The constitutive relationship of the cohesive elements was defined using the traction-separation law and the delamination evolution was defined using B-K law. Plies of the laminate were meshed using 3D liner hexahedral elements, and interfaces were meshed using liner cohesive elements. There are totally 23016 linear hexahedral elements of type C3D8R and 21098 linear hexahedral elements of type COH3D8. Mesh parts of the FE model are shown in Fig. 12. Material properties of three material systems are shown in Table 3.

4.2 Numerical results and discussion

The ultimate strengths predicted by numerical simulation are compared with experimental results in Fig. 13, and Table 4 is the averaged stress and strain on the boundary with the prescribed displacement loads, all of which show good agreement with the experiment. It can be seen that the stress-strain curves before final failure caused by fiber breakage are quite straight, which means matrix damage does not influence the whole stiffness of the laminate. The slopes of T300/5228 and T300/5428 are nearly the same, while T700/5428 has a lower slope, and this is because the difference in tensile modulus of unidirectional laminates. All the three curves drop abruptly after final failure.

Fig. 14 shows the simulated damage patterns immediately after final failure of open-hole tension laminates. It can be seen that there's obvious difference between three material types, which are consistent with experimental results. T300/5228 laminate has a brittle failure pattern, in which matrix dilatation and distortion failure occurs in a limited zone on both sides of the hole, perpendicular to the loading direction. Fiber tensile failure traverse 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, while in 90° plies there is little fiber compressive failure near the hole caused by Poisson's effect. In contrast with T300/5228, T300/5428 has almost the same fiber strength but lower matrix strength, whose damage patterns are quite different. There is much severer matrix dilatation and distortion damages before final failure in all plies, especially the matrix distortion damage of 0° plies in the vicinity of the hole which effectively relieves the stress concentration. In $\pm 45^\circ$ plies the outline of matrix failure patterns are quite parallel with the fiber direction, which at some

extend replaces fiber breakage at final failure. T700/5428 has a much higher fiber tensile strength and the same matrix type as T300/5428, and its high strength of open-hole tensile laminate is mainly attributed to the fiber. There is extensive matrix dilatational and distortional failure in $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies, while fiber tensile failure only occurs in 0° plies. In all of the three simulated damage patterns, each type of damage is slightly sever in inner plies than outer plies, which is caused by different boundary conditions in the normal direction.

5. Conclusions

A micromechanics-based, multi-scale failure criterion, which intends to build the quantitative relation of various macro-performance and the microstructure, was proposed for progressive failure analysis of fiber-reinforced composites. For the purpose of investigating the influence of constituent properties to macro performance of composite structures, open-hole tension tests were conducted in three composite systems with various combinations of fiber and matrix, which show distinctively different failure manners. The ultimate strength and failure patterns of open-hole tension problem predicted by the multi-scale failure criterion are in good agreement with those from experiments. The modulus of fiber and matrix as well as their relative strengths result in different failure modes of composite laminates. Generally speaking, in open-hole tension tests, matrix damage in early loading stages alleviates the stress concentration in 0° ply, which effectively raises the ultimate strength of the laminate, while fiber strength is a key issue in the strength of the composites. The stress distributions in micro level are determined by the modulus of fiber and matrix respectively.

As an exploration and attempt in the development of physical mechanism based failure models, the newly proposed multi-scale failure criterion achieves the whole processes of damage identification, determination and evolution, which helps to further understand the failure mechanism of composites. The potential of multi-scale failure theory in composites' design, failure analysis and long-term life prediction needs to be further investigated, which can help designers to effectively optimize constituent constituent materials and laminate sequences, thus minimizing the cost and weight of composite structures.

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Tables

Table 1 Failure mode and critical value determination

Failure mode	Critical value	Corresponding experiment
Fiber tension	Fiber tensile strength X_{ft}	Unidirectional laminate 0° tension
Fiber compression	Fiber compressive strength X_{fc}	Unidirectional laminate 0° compression
Matrix expansion	Matrix critical first stress invariant I_{1-crit}	Unidirectional laminate 90° tension
	Influence factor μ	Unidirectional laminate 10° tension
Matrix distortion	Matrix critical Von Mises stress $\sigma_{VM-crit}$	Unidirectional laminate 10° tension

Table 2 Damage determination and material property degradation

Failure mode	Reference point	Failure criteria	Micro property degradation
Fiber tension	F1~F6(Square) F1~F8(Hexagon)	$\sigma_{f1} > X_{ft}$	Fiber E_1
Fiber compression	F1~F6(Square) F1~F8(Hexagon))	$\sigma_{f1} < -X_{fc}$	Fiber E_1
Matrix expansion	M1~M10(Square) M1~M13(Hexagon)	$I_1 + \mu\sigma_{VM}^2 > I_{1-crit}$	Matrix E, ν
Matrix distortion	M1~M10(Square) M1~M13(Hexagon)	$\sigma_{VM} > \sigma_{VM-crit}$	Matrix E, ν

Note: σ_{f1} is fiber stress, X_{ft} 、 X_{fc} are fiber's tensile strength and compressive strength, I_1 is the first invariant of stress, σ_{VM} is von-mises stress, μ is influence factor.

Table 3 Material properties of UD laminate

Material properties	T300/5228	T300/5428	T700/5428
Fiber volume fraction, V_f	0.63	0.63	0.63
Longitudinal modulus, E_1 (GPa)	142	145	125
Transverse modulus, $E_2=E_3$ (GPa)	9.46	9.74	7.8
In-plane shear modulus, $G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	5.6	5.6	5.6
Transverse shear modulus, G_{23} (GPa)	5.6	5.6	5.6
In-plane Poisson's ratio, $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.32	0.32	0.32

Transverse Poisson's ratio, ν_{23}	0.35	0.32	0.32
Longitudinal thermal coefficient, $\alpha_1(10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C})$	-1.50E-07	2.80E-07	-9.70E-07
Transverse thermal coefficient, $\alpha_2(10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C})$	3.54E-05	2.77E-05	2.09E-05

Table 4 Comparison of simulated strength with experimental strength of open-hole tension

Material type	Experimental strength(MPa)	Simulated strength(MPa)	Error(%)
T300/5228	325	311	4.3
T300/5428	375	351	6.4
T700/5428	517	493	4.6

Figure captions

Fig. 1 Composite macro-meso transition: (a) ply, (b) fiber arrangement assumption, (c) RVE

Fig. 2 Representative distributions of fiber and matrix: (a) square, (b) hexagon

Fig. 3 Representative volume element (RVE) and reference points chosen: (a) square RVE, (b) hexagon RVE

Fig. 4 Failure envelope for polymer in composites

Fig. 5 Failure envelope of matrix

Fig. 6 Flowchart for damage determination and evolution

Fig. 7 Geometry of open-hole tension specimen

Fig. 8 Load-displacement curve and fracture morphology of T300/5228 OHT specimen

Fig. 9 Load-displacement curve and fracture morphology of T300/5428 OHT specimen

Fig. 10 Load-displacement curve and fracture morphology of T700/5428 OHT specimen

Fig. 11 Modeling strategy of open-hole tensile laminate

Fig. 12 FE model of open-hole tension laminate

Fig. 13 The simulated stress-strain curves of open-hole tension tests

Fig. 14 The simulated damage patterns immediately after final failure of open-hole tension:

a)T300/5228, b)T300/5428, c)T700/5428

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